

Application of vague sets for selecting the High school of the children

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Abstract:

Vague set is very much useful in providing of a flexible model to elaborate uncertainty and vagueness involved in decision making. In this paper, to measure the calibre of each school basing on the skills. Its solution is obtained by looking shortest distance between each school and skills respectively. Since the potential of the society depends upon the role of students and their services build the prosperous and sophisticated society. As per psychology, if a student has the required competence and positive attitudes towards a subject in terms of interest, attitude, memory, knowledge, environment, and career, then the student will attain more in that subject. To consider this kind of uncertain issues, fuzzy set and vague set are found to be appropriate due to their inherent characteristics to deal with incomplete and imprecise information. In this study, vague set-based approaches are proposed to help the student to choose an appropriate school and consequently provide a high-quality skills or input to the society particularly in that field. The main purpose of the article is to analyse schools features in terms of skills like Communication Skills, Logical Skills, Visualisation Of concepts, Scientific Knowledge and

Socio-economic and then forecast the appropriate school for making the career secure so that the student can easily explore much in that vicinity

Keywords:

Vague set, Similarity Measures. Student school selection

1. Introduction

Zadeh [14] was the first to establish the idea of a fuzzy set. The fuzzy set can express the state between “belong to” and “not belong to” by assigning a membership degree between 0 and 1 to items with respect to a set. As a result, fuzzy sets can be used to explain a large number of uncertainties that aren't adequately represented by classical sets. Since its inception, fuzzy set hypothesis has been employed in various applications, counting automatic control, pattern recognition, and decision-making. The hypothesis of fuzzy sets has been found to be unsatisfactory in many actual circumstances. As a result, numerous higher theories have arisen over time, such as vague sets (VSS), Pythagorean fuzzy sets, q-rung fuzzy sets given by Lin (2020) and so on. vague sets by Gowh and buhereis a higher hypothesis that is a notion of fuzzy sets that ask specialists to provide non-membership opinions on set elements. As a result, vague set (VSS) are frequently employed in pattern recognition applications suggested by W.L.Gahu, D.J. Buehrer[13] vague sets. The tools that are frequently employed in those application challenges are similarity and distance measures. These two ideas are complimentary in the sense that by subtracting one from a unit, one can be derived from the other. Similarity measure can be used to solve issues in a range of contexts, like decision making, machine learning, and pattern detection suggested by Wei (2017, 2018).

2. Preliminaries:

Here we give a review of some definitions and results which are in Gau.w.L and Buhere .D.j [13] ,Nageswararao.B, Ramakrishana.N and Eswarlal.T[6],[7] ,[8],[9].

Definition [12] 2.1: Let X be a non-empty set. A fuzzy set A drawn from X is defined as $A = \{x, \mu_A(x) : x \in X\}$, where $\mu_A(x) : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is the membership function of the fuzzy set A

The membership degrees are calculated using membership functions with

$\mu_A(X)$ where X is considered as the subject.

Definition [12] 2.2: The Hamming distance between the fuzzy sets can be defined by

$$d(A, B) = \sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_A(x_i) - \mu_B(x_i)|, \text{ where } x_i \in X$$

Definition [12] 2.3: The Euclidean distance between the fuzzy sets can be defined by

$$d(A, B) = \sum_{i=1}^n (\sqrt{[\mu_A(x_i) - \mu_B(x_i)]})^2, \text{ where } x_i \in X$$

In this section we give a review of some definitions and results which are in Gau.w.Land Buhere.D.j[8]Nageswararao.B,Ramakrishana.N and Eswarlal.T[3],[4],[5],[6].

Definition [1]2.1: Let X be a non-empty set. A fuzzy set A drawn from X is defined as $A = \{x, m_A(x) : x \in X\}$, where $m_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is the membership function of the fuzzy set A .

Definition[8] 2.2: A vague set A in the universe of discourse X is a pair $A = (m_A, n_A)$ where $m_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $n_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $m_A(x) + n_A(x) \leq 1$ for all x in X. Here m_A is called the membership function and n_A is called non-membership function and also called truth function and false function respectively.

Definition 2.3 [4] The vague set A of a set X with $t_A(x)=0$ and $f_A(x)=1$, for all $x \in X$ is called the zero vague set of X. It is denoted by $\bar{0}=(0,1)$.

Definition 2.4 [5] The vague set A of a set X with $t_A(x)=1$ and $f_A(x)=0$, for $x \in$,for all $x \in X$ is called the unit vague set of X. It is denoted by $\bar{1}=(1,0)$.

3. Application vague sets in testing various skills of High school children

Let $P = \{S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4, S_5\}$ represent the set of five schools and the vague value of the schools and subjects initially identified by analyst .Therefore the set of all subjects of $S = \{\text{English, Mathematics, Physical science, Natural Science, Social studies}\}$.

Table 3.1 The Vague values of schools and Subjects:

	English	Mathematics	Physical science	Natural Science	Social studies
S ₁	(0.3, 0.1)	(0.4, 0.2)	(0.5, 0.3)	(0.4, 0.2)	(0.5, 0.4)
S ₂	(0.4, 0.1)	(0.5, 0.4)	(0.3, 0.4)	(0.5, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.2)
S ₃	(0.4, 0.2)	(0.5, 0.1)	(0.3, 0.1)	(0.4, 0.2)	(0.6, 0.3)
S ₄	(0.5, 0.3)	(0.6 0.2)	(0.5, 0.1)	(0.5, 0.2)	(0.7, 0.1)
S ₅	(0.6, 0.3)	(0.7, 0.1)	(0.5, 0.1)	(0.6, 0.2)	(0.6, 0.1)

Table 3.2 The vague values of Schools and skills:

Let S represent the Skills, where S= {Communication Skills, Logical Skills, Visualisation Of concepts, Scientific Knowledge, Socio-economic }.Here we calculate the distance between schools and skills using proposed similarity measure. The student is likely to have the skills if there is a close proximity between the schools and skills.

The vague values of Schools and skills:

	Communication Skills	Logical skills	Visualisation Of concepts	Scientific Knowledge	Socio-economic
S ₁	(0.4, 0.1)	(0.5,0.2)	(0.7, 0.2)	(0.5, 0.1)	(0.7 , 0.1)
S ₂	(0.4, 0.2)	(0.7, 0.1)	(0.4, 0.2)	(0.5, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.2)
S ₃	(0.3, 0.1)	(0.4, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.3)	(0.7 ,0.2)	(0.6, 0.1)
S ₄	(0.4, 0.2)	(0.4, 0.5)	(0.6, 0.2)	(0.3, 0.3)	(0.2, 0.5)
S ₅	(0.5, 0.2)	(0.4,0.2)	(0.6,0.2)	(0.6, 0.1)	(0.6, 0.3)

Table: 3.3: The Distance between Schools and Skills:

The distance between schools and Skills using proposed similarity measure

The distance between the schools and the set of skills which is identified by

$$d(A,B)= [\frac{1}{2n} (t_A(x_i) - t_B(x_i))^2 + (f_A(x_i) - f_B(x_i))^2]^{1/2}$$

Skills	Communication skills	Logical skills	Visualisation Of concepts	Scientific Knowledge	Socio-economic
S ₁	0.05	0.05	0.118	0.07071	0.18028
S ₂	0.05	0.18028	0.118	0.5	0.5
S ₃	0.07071	0.1118	0.14142	0.150	0.10
S ₄	0.07071	0.18028	0.07071	0.1118	0.32016
S ₅	0.0707	0.15811	0.07071	0.05	0.10

Conclusion:

3.4 From the above table the following points observed in my research

From the last table we have concluded the following

1. School S₁ is able to cater the Socio-Economic skills
2. School S₂ is able to cater the skill logical thinking
3. School S₃ is able to cater the Socio-Economic skills
4. School S₄ is able to cater the skills of Scientific Knowledge, logical thinking and Communication skills
5. School S₅ is able to cater the Communication skills

Conclusion: 3.5

Using the suggested similarity measures on Vague sets (VSS), this portion of work explain how to decide the skills by using vague sets. For selecting the High school of the children through various skills, idea of distance measures on Vague sets (VSS), to resolve uncertainty. This paper’s chief contribution is the conception of a distance-based in testing various skills of High school children using decision-making system for Vague sets (VSs).The ability of Vague sets (VSs) to satisfactorily deal with incorrectness, vagueness and uncertainty while incorporate the idea of neutrality to some extent is the main validation for the choice. It helps the parents and students to select the right school for better future

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